

DEVANT BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENTS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ISSUES OF ITS ELIMINATION

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Abstract. This article deal with deviant behaviorial attitudes and socio-psychological issues of adolescents. The article analyzes the essence and essence of the concept of devivative behavior, the deviant behavior and doctrine of the Oriental philosophers regarding deviation, deviant behaviorial adolescents and their psychological peculiarities.

Key words: deviant behavior, adolescence, youth, behavioral disorder, eastern perceptions, rule of law, morality, anxieties, delusional behavior, alcoholism, education, school, teacher, parent, constructive behavior.

ДЕВАНТНОЕ ПОВЕДЕНИЕ У ПОДРОСТКОВ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ВОПРОСЫ ЕГО ЛИКВИДАЦИИ

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются девиантные поведенческие установки и социально-психологические проблемы подростков. В статье анализируются суть и суть понятия девиативного поведения, девиантного поведения и учения восточных философов относительно девиации, девиантного поведения подростков и их психологических особенностей.

Ключевые слова: девиантное поведение, подростковый возраст, молодость, расстройство поведения, восточное мировоззрение, законность, мораль, тревоги, бредовое поведение, алкоголизм, образование, школа, учитель, родитель, конструктивное поведение.

"Deviant" in Latin means "deviation" - "refusal, denial." The concept of deviant is used in the sense of deviant behavior, non-recognition of the norms of social life, disobedience to it. The concept of deviant behavior means that the behavior of minors deviates from social rules accepted in society and is characterized by non-compliance and violation of these rules. Deviant behavior is especially common among minors[1,76]. During this period, the personal characteristics of minors are formed, their self-awareness and knowledge of the world are determined. However, the

formation and development of personality is a complex process that can be accompanied by specific difficulties and deviations, internal contradictions, and an inability to adapt to various situations of social life. Young people with deviant character often do not attend classes at school, run away from home, become nannies, beg, drink alcohol, and indulge in drug addiction. As a result, they tend to break the law and commit crimes.

In the early periods of human history, the processes of social deviations and deviant behavior were considered immoral and were regulated primarily through religious norms. Since ancient times, the Turanian peoples also had a negative attitude towards social deviations, and this attitude was reflected in Zoroastrianism, Buddhism and other ancient Turanian religious teachings. The founder of the Aristotelian movement in the medieval Muslim East in Movoraunahr is the encyclopedist Abu Nasr al-Farabi. Following Aristotle, Farby divides philosophy into two parts: theoretical and practical, and includes ethics in practical philosophy. Problems of deviation from moral standards were raised in such works as “On Finding Happiness”, “The Wisdom of a Statesman”, “The City of Virtuous People”. Alloma assigns a large place to virtue in his views. Like Aristotle, he divides the virtues into two parts - virtuous speech and virtuous behavior and emphasizes their intermediate features. According to our great countryman, mature character must be the product of habits that direct it to good deeds. Virtue of character is related to the degree to which standards of behavior are adhered to. Farobi says that some people become very relaxed due to excessive indulgence, eating and drinking, and applying lipstick to a woman, their will weakens, and the feeling of hatred and malice in the treatise disappears. For one who gives all his energy to himself, the sublime begins to serve the lower, that is, the ability to think is in the service of the forces of anger and passion, and the action of these forces is associated with food and drunkenness and the satisfaction of sensual lust.

Abu Rayhan Beruni is one of our great ancestors, who left a deep mark on the science of ethics, social and natural sciences in general. In his works, Abu Rayhan Beruni serves as the basis for calculating the direction of the emergence of the natural environment and social deviations in the formation of positive or negative customs and behavior of people and nations. “...not because of the color, image, character and moral structures (of people), but also because of the diversity of soil, water, air and places where (people) live” [2.89].

In the period before the Mongol invasion in the Middle Ages, in addition to the encyclopedist scholars mentioned above, into the theoretical or practical fields of moral science. Among the scholars named above, the mystics paid special attention to moral education, correction and purification.

But the Mongol invasion destroyed cultural life in the Muslim East. Only during the time of the

sorcerer Amir Temur did the development of science and art return to its normal course. The era of Timur and the Timurids continues to amaze the world as the golden age of the development of science and culture. During this period, hundreds of encyclopedist scientists, great poets and artists appeared. Among them, the great Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi is of particular importance.

Not only the high artistry of his works, but also his philosophical and moral views have not lost their spiritual and moral significance.

“Deviant behavior is divided into two types: the first type is a rejection of mental norms, manifested by asthenic, schizoid and psychopathological deficits. The second type is represented by violations of social and cultural norms and disobedience of laws, criminal acts. At the same time, offenses also belong to this type. Adolescence is the most important period in the development of personality; it is a period of hesitation, comparison of oneself with peers and others, dissatisfaction with one’s condition and appearance. The reason is that during this period the teenager gradually realizes the need and begins to achieve a certain freedom; accordingly, he acquires the ability to make decisions, that is, he begins to act responsibly, based on the laws of social development. In this regard, the period of adolescence is filled with various contradictory experiences, difficulties and crises. Therefore, this period is a period of loss of childhood feelings, feelings of anxiety and the emergence of psychological discomfort.

Adolescence is often called a period of disproportional development. At this age, attention is paid to one’s own physical characteristics, the reaction to the opinions of others intensifies, and the feeling of personal pride and resentment increases. Physical defects are often exaggerated. First of all, not only physical changes, but also the new social role of a teenager are the reasons for increased attention to one’s body compared to childhood. People around them expect that a teenager will be able to cope with certain developmental problems on his own, to the detriment of physical maturity. Trying to get out of the care of adults, a teenager is looking for an opportunity to temporarily express his growing “I” in order to feel free [3, 221]. He finds this in a leisure environment. Free time is a priority in a teenager’s life. Minors spend this time outside the home, in the company of peers. Parents have no influence on a teenager's communication outside of school, supposedly in order to protect their children from unwanted contact. The result is teenagers who like to be alone. The morality of adolescents is primarily influenced by the external social environment (microenvironment: family, class, school conditions, relationships with other members of this environment), as well as the individual characteristics of the adolescent’s reaction to various “life failures.”

Behavioral deviations, expressed in various forms of adolescent maladjustment, are the result of unhealthy psychosocial development and disruption of the socialization process. Indeed,

during this period, a teenager tries to realize himself in all aspects, to find his place among other people, he looks with desire at some qualities in the actions and actions of the adults around him, and it is difficult for him not to find these qualities in himself. Sometimes he even feels inferior. At such a time, it is necessary for the child's close people, first of all his parents and teacher-trainer, to lend a helping hand. It is known that a child first sees the traits and qualities of his parents, and then begins to compare them with others. Therefore, parents must be able to find a way to the hearts of their children. Children with deviant behavior (running away from school, constantly disturbing their peers, teasing classmates) need all kinds of support from adults. Parents should provide moral support to the child with the help of the class teacher, teacher and school psychologists.

“Adolescence is the period when his worldview, beliefs, views, principles, self-awareness, assessment, etc. are formed. While a child of primary school age acts on the instructions of adults or his random, involuntary desires, a teenager begins to organize his activities based on certain principles, beliefs and personal views. In the development of a teenager's personality, morality and individual consciousness are of particular importance. In this case, students' assimilation of moral concepts and their application in life plays an important role. The process of developing universal feelings in a student faces contradictions in beliefs, convictions and points of view. Observing social life and acquiring the skills a person needs in it gives him the opportunity to analyze the behavior of adults. As a result, life skills such as assessing the behavior and manners of older people in emergency situations begin to develop.

In the process of studying the socio-psychological factors of crime and deviant behavior of minors, it was found that they are influenced to a greater extent by:

1. Disagreements between minors and adults and among themselves (in the family, at school, at the place of residence);
2. Minors who join general and other informal groups on the street and participate in their activities are subject to pressure from the leaders of these groups;
3. Interaction of minors with adults (often previously convicted), who incline them to a particular violation or crime, as well as involving them in regular use of alcohol and drugs;
4. Mistakes made in the process of teaching minors separately (in the family) and in the majority (at school) by educators (parents) mothers, teachers) do not know or cannot adequately understand the age and socio-psychological characteristics of adolescents [4,125]лик ёки етарли англай олмасликларидир [4,125].

Internal conflict is a state of personality structure in which there are simultaneously several opposing motives, goals and value orientations, in which a person does not have the

strength to fight at the moment, that is, he experiences difficulties with control. his behavior was formed on this basis.

In short, internal conflict is a state of internal personality structure that enhances destructive behavior and is characterized by the presence of internal contradictions. In this regard, internal conflicts can be explained as follows, that is, internal conflict arises as a result of the interaction of elements of a person's internal structure; interests, goals, desires and motives of different natures and conflicting with each other in the internal structure of a person act as parties to an internal conflict.

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